

THE ROLE AND TASKS OF MICE TOURISM IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF FREE TOURIST ZONES IN UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation. This scientific article describes in detail the free tourist zones and MICE tourism, the current conditions for the development of free MICE tourism in Uzbekistan, the prospects for the development of MICE tourism and its role in the formation of tourism infrastructure. Here are some suggestions on how to look or get an appointment for MICE tourism in the area.

Keywords: Free tourist zone, MICE tourism, Charvak, investment, technology, conference, business.

In recent years, the attention paid to tourism in our country has been at a high level. In accordance with the Presidential Decree No. PF-4861 of December 2, 2016 "On measures to ensure the accelerated development of tourism in the Republic of Uzbekistan", tourism was granted the status of a key sector of the economy. To date, tourism has established itself as a part of the economy, and in 2019 the export of tourist services amounted to \$ 1.3 billion, which is 26.1 times more than in 2018 (\$ 1 billion). percent increase. However, during the pandemic, this figure was very low not only in Uzbekistan, but in the whole world.

According to the World Tourism Organization, in 2019, more than 1.5 billion international trips were made worldwide for tourism purposes. In today's era of globalization, the specialized development of cities to a certain extent is accelerating the development of industries and sectors. In this regard, the establishment of free economic zones, the creation of a set of entrepreneurs in one activity, serves to increase competitiveness, improve the quality of services and products.

'Chapter 4, Article 17 of the Law of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 18, 2019" On Tourism "defines tourist zones as follows:

"There are certain boundaries, one or more tourist resources (natural, historical, socio-cultural, medical, health facilities, as well as other facilities that can meet the needs of tourists and excursionists), inbound tourism and domestic tourism, tourism The area created for the development of industry, protection and rational use of tourist resources is a tourist zone. In addition, free tourist zones are equated to free economic zones, which means that in large areas, businesses are concentrated in one large area.

Therefore, the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On additional measures to increase the efficiency of free economic zones and small industrial zones" of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan Regulations on the procedure for selection of investment projects for placement in the territory of free economic zones and registration of participants of free economic zones also applies.

When considering the placement of a particular project in a free tourist zone, it is necessary to pay attention to the following:

- Investments are made at the expense of entrepreneurs' own funds and loans attracted by them without providing a state guarantee of Uzbekistan;
- Financial capacity of the investor, availability of technical and technological base; expediency of the investment project (convenient placement of the investment project, the number of jobs created, the impact on infrastructure changes in the region and the industry as a whole, the availability of the necessary infrastructure to use existing capacity);
- Availability of a management system in the investment project that meets international standards;
- Information on the availability of modern energy-saving systems and technologies, including a list of equipment and process lines.

Aimed at attracting foreign direct investment, meeting the criteria of the world's leading transnational hotel chains and catering brands, while also seeking to attract locals as employees giving priority to projects is important.

According to the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the establishment of a free tourist zone" Charvak ", attracting investment in areas with high tourism potential, having modern tourism infrastructure, In order to develop tour routes, further develop the transport network, establish the use of alternative energy-saving equipment, the free tourist zone "Charvak" was established. Today, Charvak is one of the regions of Uzbekistan with high tourist potential. Not only foreign guests but also locals visit a lot. It has all the necessary communications and internet access. Most importantly, you can have an interesting rest in the pools. It is possible to organize business meetings in the heart of nature, and it is important that the transport is well organized.

Today, MICE tourism is one of the main areas of tourism development in developed countries. According to the data, in 2019, 45% of Russian tourism was business tourism. It should be noted that this is due to the fact that entrepreneurs work with many foreign partners, leave the country and come in with many partners.

In 2019, 6,748,500 tourists visited Uzbekistan, and in 2018 the figure was 5,346,200. The largest number of tourists came from Central Asia, with 5,764,500 people. The number of visitors from the CIS countries was 495,600. The number of visitors from far abroad countries was 488,400,000. Most of the tourists came from Kazakhstan, Tajikistan, Kyrgyzstan, Turkmenistan, the Russian Federation, Turkey, Afghanistan, China, the Republic of Korea and India for various purposes. The picture below shows the targets of tourists arriving in 2019, with the number of business visitors in Uzbekistan being very low and still at 2.7%, along with other tourism targets. Therefore, there is a lot of work to be done in our country in this regard, and it would be expedient to provide the general public with information about

MICE tourism, to obtain a separate summary of MICE tourism indicators in areas with developed tourism.

MICE tourism is one of the most sustainable types of tourism in free tourist areas. This tourism is not yet well developed in Uzbekistan and is a new type of tourism. However, the foundations for the development of MICE tourism in our country have already been laid, and there are no obstacles to establishing business cooperation, meetings and conferences within the law. However, there are many shortcomings in this regard, and finding ways to overcome them and conducting research is one of the main tasks of every tourist entity. Given that the free tourist zones include a large complex of complexes, it is not difficult to understand that the development of MICE tourism there will be more effective.

MICE tourism includes business trips related to meetings, conferences, and the organization and conduct of various events. The development of MICE tourism is an effective solution to improving interstate, intergovernmental and inter-agency relations, signing business and cooperation agreements, exchanging mutually beneficial proposals, finding new ideas, resolving discussions and debates. In particular, the link between business and tourism will benefit both partners. To this end, it is important to increase the number of facilities in the free tourist zones that contribute to the development of MICE tourism, to attract businesses.

MICE tourism development contributes to the development of the country's business image. Because in MICE tourism, mainly:

- Carrying out business and cooperation activities of businessmen and business entities from one place to another,
- Organize business meetings and events,
- Establish new partnerships,

- Staff training and participation in trainings;
- Organization of group trips;
- Sending trips to encourage successful employees;
- It is planned to organize events to improve the image of the enterprise.

The following facilities will be included in the development of MICE tourism:

1. Conference halls;
2. Working offices;
3. Event halls;
4. Large shopping centers;
5. Hotel halls;
6. Restaurants and similar facilities for meetings.

MICE tourism first appeared in developed western countries and today is dominated by large companies and organizations. Its centers are the United States, Great Britain, Germany, Australia, France and Spain. In the East, China can be called the center of business meetings. MICE tourism is a more profitable type of tourism than other types of tourism. This is due to the fact that the process of currency exchange takes place more, and higher prices play a greater role than individual travel. In addition, the main task of business tourism is to make a good impression on future partners of the company by using high-quality services. Therefore, economic savings in such a situation do not give good results.

The development of business tourism in the Republic of Uzbekistan will help to attract more business partners and foreign investors, to create a business culture in the country. Our country has all the opportunities to develop MICE tourism. In particular, according to the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the State Program to Support the Development of Small Business and Private Entrepreneurship", all the tasks to be performed in the formation of entrepreneurial activity in the country given. In addition, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Investments and Investment Activities" allows all investment activities, regulates investment activities and provides benefits.

Based on these data, it should be noted that not only the development of MICE tourism in free tourist zones, but also the development of entrepreneurs throughout the country and the rational use of opportunities, the development of tourist zones, domestic and foreign tourism, increasing the share of tourism in GDP and serves to enhance the business culture.

Based on the above, the following proposals can be made for the development of business tourism in free tourist zones:

1. Increase the number of business events in all regions;
2. Increasing the number of recreational facilities in tourist areas;
3. Increasing the number of service facilities that meet international standards;
4. Introduction of modern communication technologies in all regions;
5. Introduce special travel tickets for business travelers;
6. Strengthening security measures in free tourist areas;
7. Creating a healthy competitive environment for entrepreneurs;
8. Establish a car rental system in free tourist zones;
9. Improving the system of combating corruption in free tourist zones and taking measures against it.

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